

Design Development and Evaluation of Bilayer Tablet Using Eprosartan Mesylate for the Treatment of Hypertension

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Available Online: 25th August, 2017

ABSTRACT

The aim of present study is to formulate Eprosartan Mesylate sustained release (SR) and immediate release (IR) bilayer tablet by different concentration of Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) and HPMC K 100 M to control the release pattern. The sustained release layer of Eprosartan Mesylate was prepared by using different grades of HPMC like, HPMC K-100, HPMC along with other excipients by direct compression technique. The immediate release layer of Eprosartan Mesylate was prepared by Cross carmellose sodium and Sodium starch glycolate by direct compression technique. The powders were evaluated for their flow properties and the finished tablets were evaluated for their physical parameters. The both immediate release and sustained release layers of Eprosartan Mesylate were characterized by FT-IR and in vitro dissolution studies. The drug release study of Eprosartan Mesylate was evaluated using USP-II paddle type dissolution apparatus. The release rate of Eprosartan Mesylate in immediate release layer was studied for 1hr in 0.1 N HCL media and that of Eprosartan Mesylate in sustained release layer was studied for 12 hr in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer media. From the nine batches S9 batch showed good release behaviour 98.82% of drug is released over 12 hours. Eprosartan Mesylate is a poorly water soluble (BCS class II) antihypertensive drug. Due to the poor water solubility of this drug, its bioavailability is dissolution rate-limited.

Keywords: Bi-layer tablet, Sustained Release, Immediate Release, Eprosartan Mesylate.

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, interest in developing a combination of two or more Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API) in a single dosage form (bi-layer tablet) has increased in the pharmaceutical industry, promoting patient convenience and compliance. Bi-layer tablets can be a primary option to avoid chemical incompatibilities between APIs by physical separation, and to enable the development of different drug release profiles (immediate release with extended release)^{1,2}. In the last decade, interest in developing a combination of two or more Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API) in a single dosage form (bilayer tablet) has increased. The main objective of combination therapy is to encourage the utilization of lower doses of drugs to treat patients and also to minimize dose dependent side effect and adverse reactions³. To overcome the drawbacks of single layer combination tablet this concept was came into force⁴. Bilayer tablets can be a primary option to avoid chemical incompatibilities between API by physical separation, and to enable the development of different drug release profiles (immediate release with extended release)⁵.

Eprosartan Mesylate is Angiotensin II (formed from angiotensin I in a reaction catalyzed by angiotensin-converting enzyme [kininase II]), a potent vasoconstrictor, is the principal pressor agent of the renin-angiotensin

system. Angiotensin II also stimulates aldosterone synthesis and secretion by the adrenal cortex, cardiac contraction, renal resorption of sodium, activity of the sympathetic nervous system, and smooth muscle cell growth. Eprosartan blocks the vasoconstrictor and aldosterone-secreting effects of angiotensin II by selectively blocking the binding of angiotensin II to the AT1 receptor found in many tissues (e.g., vascular smooth muscle, adrenal gland). There is also an AT2 receptor found in many tissues but it is not known to be associated with cardiovascular homeostasis. Eprosartan does not exhibit any partial agonist activity at the AT1 receptor. Its affinity for the AT1 receptor is 1,000 times greater than for the AT2 receptor. *In vitro* binding studies indicate that eprosartan is a reversible, competitive inhibitor of the AT1 receptor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eprosartan Mesylate obtained as gift sample from Mylan Laboratories, Sinner, Nashik and HPMC were obtained as gift sample from Stadmed Pvt.Ltd, Kolkata. Sodium starch glycolate, microcrystalline cellulose, Magnesium stearate and HPMC K100 were obtained as gift sample from Merck specialties Private Limited. PVP K 30 was obtained as gift sample from Lobachem private limited, Mumbai. All other chemicals/reagents used were of analytical grade.

*Ftir Spectroscopy*⁷

The drug and optimised formulation were characterized by IR spectroscopy using a FTIR 8400S (Shimadzu, Japan). The spectra were taken in the range of 4000–500 cm⁻¹.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Study

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study of Bilayer tablets was performed using a Toledo DSC (METTLER STAR SW 9.01) to determine the drug excipients compatibility study. The analysis was performed at a rate 5 °C min⁻¹ from 50 to 300°C temperature range under nitrogen flow of 25 mL min⁻¹.

Formulation and characterization of bilayer tablets

The bilayer tablets of Eprosartan Mesylate were prepared by the direct compression method. The drug and polymers for both IR and SR layer were passed through a # 60 sieve before their use in the formulation.

Preparation of Solid Dispersions of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Layer

Various carriers are used to make solid dispersions. In the present study PEG 4000 was used as a hydrophilic carrier in the preparation of solid dispersion. These solid dispersions were prepared by using Solvent Evaporation Method. These were used in different ratios with respect to plain drug. Different drug: polymers ratios were employed as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3,1:4, 1:5 & solid dispersions were prepared by solvent evaporation method Polymers employed was PEG 4000

*Solvent evaporation method*¹⁰⁻¹¹

Solid dispersions Eprosartan Mesylate was prepared using PEG 4000 by solvent evaporation method in various weight ratios.

Steps in the preparation of solid dispersion by solvent evaporation:

Drug & polymer (PEG 4000) mixtures were dissolved in methanol in the ratio 1:1, 1:2, 1:3,1:4, 1:5.

The solutions were made homogeneous by continuous stirring and solvent was evaporated by subjecting the solution with constant stirring at 70 to 80°C on water bath till complete evaporation of solvent.

The obtained solid dispersions were air dried & subsequently pulverized by triturating in pestle-mortar & screened through 60 mesh sieve.

Solubility Study

The solid dispersions were subjected for solubility studies to evaluate the effect of different carriers and carrier ratios on the aqueous solubility of Eprosartan Mesylate. Eprosartan Mesylate can be practically insoluble in water. An excess amount of the sample solid dispersion was placed in contact with distilled water. The samples were shaken for 48 hours at 37 °C in an orbital shaker. The supernatant was filtered through a whatmann filter paper. The filtrate was suitably diluted to 10 ppm and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 230 nm. All experiments were conducted in triplicate.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction

PXRD analysis was done by irradiating the samples with monochromatized Cu K α radiation at a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 50 mA. The samples were scanned in increments of 0.02° from 5° to 60° (diffraction angle 2 θ) at a rate of 1s per step using a zero background sample

holder, employing a Brucker AXS D8 Advance Diffractometer with Lynx Eye Detector.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The powdered sample (3 mg) was hermetically sealed in aluminum pans and heated at a constant rate of 10°C/min, over a temperature range of 30–300°C with nitrogen flow rate of 30 ml/min. Thermograms of the samples were obtained using differential scanning Calorimetry (METTLER STAR SW 9.01). Thermal analysis data were recorded with Lab Mettler software programs. Indium standard was used to calibrate the DSC temperature and enthalpy scale.

Selection of most satisfactory formulation

From all the above formulations, Solid dispersion of Eprosartan Mesylate - PEG 4000 (1:3) showing Maximum *in-vitro* drug release. Hence this inclusion complex showing maximum dissolution rate was converted to cost effective tablet formulations.

Formulation and Preparation of the IR Layer^{8,9}

The IR ingredients (Table 2) were accurately weighed and added into the blender in ascending order. The powder mix was blended for 20 min. to obtain uniform distribution of the drug in formulation and subjected for preformulation studies. All the formulation components were passed through sieve #60, weighed, mixed, and compressed into tablet using 8mm punch on Rotary tablet minipress-I (Rimek, Karnavati Engineering Ltd., Mehsana, Gujarat).

Formulation and Preparation of the SR Layer^{10,11}

The SR ingredients were accurately weighed and added into the blender in ascending order. The powder mix was blended for 20 min. to obtain uniform distribution of the drug in formulation and subjected for preformulation studies. Tablets were prepared by direct compression method with 12 mm stainless steel punch using rotary press (Karnavati Minitab, India). Compression force for all the tablets was adjusted to get tablets of hardness 4-6 kg/cm². Hardness was measured by Monsanto type hardness tester (Coslab). Weight of were adjusted to 300 mg of all compress tablets.

Formulation of Bilayer Tablet

In the present study bilayer tablet was prepared manually using single station punching machine. Accurately weighed amount of SR powder mix was fed manually into die cavity. SR layer was compressed at mild compression

Table 1: Composition of various solid dispersions by solvent evaporation method.

Sr. No.	Drug	Polymer	Ratio	Method of preparation
1.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:1	SE
2.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:2	SE
3.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:3	SE
4.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:4	SE
5.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:5	SE

Table 2: Composition of various tablets prepared Eprosartan Mesylate IR layer.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
SD(Eprosartan Mesylate)	146	146	146	146	146	146	146	146	146
SSG	04	04	04	08	08	08	12	12	12
CCS	4	6	8	4	6	8	4	6	8
MCC	45	44	42	42	41	39	39	38	36
Magnesium stearate	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02
Talc	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02
Aerosil	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Colour	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

(All quantities are in mg)

Table 3: Composition of various tablets prepared Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer.

Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Eprosartan Mesylate	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
HPMC	6	9	12	6	9	12	6	9	12
HPMC K 100 M	9	9	9	18	18	18	27	27	27
PVP K-30	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Microcrystalline Cellulose	68	65	62	59	56	53	50	47	44
Total	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

(All quantities are in mg)

Table 4: Formulation of optimize of bi-layer tablet of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Layer (I8) and Eprosartan Mesylate SR Layer (S9).

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Formulation (I8)	Ingredients	Formulation (S9)
	Formulation of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Layer (I8)		Formulation Of Eprosartan Mesylate SR Layer (S9)	
1	SD (Eprosartan Mesylate)	146	Drug (Eprosartan Mesylate)	200
2	Sodium Starch Glycolate	12	HPMC	12
3	Cross Carmellose Sodium	06	HPMC K 100	27
4	Microcrystalline Cellulose	31	PVP K 30	12
5	Magnesium stearate	02	Magnesium stearate	02
6	Talc	02	Talc	03
7	Aerosil	0.5	Micro Crystalline Cellulose	44
8	Colour	0.5	Total	300
9	Total	200		

(All quantities are in mg)

Table 5: Solubility study of various Solid Dispersions.

Sr. No.	Drug	Polymer	Ratio	Solubility (mg/ml) \pm S.D.
1.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:1	0.790 \pm 0.011
2.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:2	1.103 \pm 0.009
3.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:3	1.132 \pm 0.021
4.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:4	1.657 \pm 0.019
5.	Eprosartan Mesylate	PEG 4000	1:5	0.922 \pm 0.016

force. After that accurately weighed IR powder mix was manually fed into the die on SR layer and compressed using 12mm circular shape concave punch on Rotary tablet minipress-I (Rimek, Karnavati Engineering Ltd., Mehsana, Gujarat). I8 batch from Eprosartan Mesylate IR layer and S9 batch from Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer were selected to form Optimized bilayer tablet (I8S9) by direct compression method. Composition of bilayer tablet was shown in table no.4

Powder characterization¹³⁻¹⁵

Angle of repose

Angle of repose was determined by using funnel method. The granules were poured from funnel that can be raised vertically until a maximum cone height 'h' was obtained. Then the diameter of the powder cone was measured and the angle of repose was calculated using the following equation. $\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$.

Bulk density

Figure 1: FTIR spectra Eprosartan Mesylate.

Table 7: Results of precompression evaluation of Eprosartan Mesylate IR layer.

Batch No.	Bulk density (gm/cm ³) ±SD	Tapped density (gm/cm ³) ±SD	Compressibility index (%)±SD	Hausner's ratio±SD	Angle of repose(θ) ±SD
I1	0.5299±0.0081	0.610±0.0154	13.16±1.246	0.75± 0.011	33.16±1.67
I2	0.5538±0.0067	0.606±0.0068	9.01±0.469	0.83± 0.015	30.88±0.32
I3	0.5296±0.0143	0.635±0.0307	16.59±0.634	0.82± 0.026	27.34±1.77
I4	0.5416±0.0145	0.635±0.0307	19.37±1.559	0.82± 0.017	30.55±0.32
I5	0.5373±0.0156	0.612±0.0073	13.65±0.126	0.81± 0.0251	30.81±0.98
I6	0.556±0.0763	0.605±0.0108	8.023±1.910	0.75± 0.015	29.23±0.72
I7	0.4398±0.073	0.597±0.0051	12.02±0.450	0.80± 0.015	30.32±0.60
I8	0.5395±0.086	0.608±0.0108	11.00±0.436	0.78± 0.026	26.76±0.40
I9	0.5253±0.019	0.604±0.0051	13.03±0.722	0.73±0.025	30.47±0.36

Table 8: Results of post compression evaluation of Eprosartan Mesylate IR layer.

Batch No.	Thickness (mm) ±SD	Hardness (kg/cm ²) ±SD	Friability (%)	Weight variation (%)±SD	Disintegration Time (Min)	Drug content (%)
I1	3.42±0.01	3.10±0.07	0.99	0.682±1.3	6.27±0.17	94.25±0.0
I2	3.42±0.07	2.70±0.367	0.77	0.229±0.6	6.41±2.01	89.52±0.0
I3	3.41±0.08	3.20±0.07	1.0	4.49±0.70	6.29±1.09	86.52±0.0
I4	3.42±0.01	3.10±0.07	1.0	0.476±0.6	6.75±0.49	93.38±0.3
I5	3.41±0.01	3.13±0.495	1.0	0.410±0.5	6.14±1.15	85..15±0.3
I6	3.42±0.07	3.16±0.041	1.0	0.476±0.3	6.54±0.51	93.19±0.0
I7	3.41±0.01	3.20±0.07	0.29	0.410±0.4	6.70±1.21	91.10±0.0
I8	3.43±0.07	3.23±0.081	0.28	0.397±0.6	6.39±0.95	97.89±0.1
I9	3.45±0.07	3.40±0.282	0.28	0.557±0.67	5.78±0.80	93.87±0.1

Bulk Density Apparent bulk density was determined by placing pre-sieved granules into a graduated cylinder and measuring the volume and weight as it is. The bulk density is calculated by using following formula. Bulk density = Weight of powder / volume of packing.

Tapped density

A quantity of 2 gm of powder from each formula was introduced into a 10 ml measuring cylinder. After a initial volume was observed, the cylinder was allow to fall under its own weight on the hard surface from the height of 2.5 cm at two second intervals. The tapping was continued

until no further change in the volume was noted. The tapped density was calculated by using following formula. Tapped density = weight of powder / tapped volume of packing.

Compressibility index

Compressibility index of granules was determined by Carr's compressibility index. Carr's index:

Compressibility Index

$$= \frac{\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Tapped Density}} \times 100$$

Figure 2: X-ray diffractogram of Eprosartan Mesylate.

Figure 3: X-ray diffractogram of physical mixture (Eprosartan Mesylate-PEG 4000).

Table 9: In-Vitro drug release of Eprosartan Mesylate IR tablet.

Time (min)	Formulation Batches (% CDR \pm SD)								
	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9
5	18.67	7.334	11.64	9.68	14.79	11.83	18.46	27.23	1.77
10	23.60	34.10	29.03	22.90	24.60	18.26	27.23	41.01	26.38
20	27.62	29.78	32.32	26.11	27.10	27.73	42.20	45.34	48.58
30	52.29	37.27	37.87	27.31	28.93	31.89	44.99	64.29	49.48
40	63.24	45.07	48.22	33.86	33.19	34.16	49.92	79.84	52.15
50	65.26	57.15	71.92	35.74	42.60	41.73	60.40	89.59	60.39
60	70.38	96.15	95.87	61.50	62.23	72.94	88.84	99.86	71.48

Table 10: Results of precompression evaluation of Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer.

Batch No.	Bulk density (gm/cm ³) \pm SD	Tapped density (gm/cm ³) \pm SD	Compressibility index (%) \pm SD	Hausner's ratio \pm SD	Angle of repose(θ) \pm SD
S1	0.615 \pm 0.0067	0.7151 \pm 0.0106	14.18 \pm 0.106	1.16 \pm 0.037	27.96 \pm 0.272
S2	0.624 \pm 0.0131	0.6854 \pm 0.0093	8.76 \pm 1.44	1.09 \pm 0.0119	27.29 \pm 1.590
S3	0.648 \pm 0.229	0.6996 \pm 0.095	10.37 \pm 0.986	1.07 \pm 0.33	28.9 \pm 1.22
S4	0.691 \pm 0.0080	0.6684 \pm 0.011	10.85 \pm 0.467	0.96 \pm 0.0026	29.60 \pm 0.494
S5	0.641 \pm 0.0025	0.7090 \pm 0.2103	13.00 \pm 1.429	1.13 \pm 0.0403	29.67 \pm 0.804
S6	0.625 \pm 0.0015	0.6793 \pm 0.0614	7.83 \pm 1.111	1.10 \pm 0.0322	26.72 \pm 0.807
S7	0.689 \pm 0.0122	0.6743 \pm 0.0273	14.12 \pm 0.735	1.84 \pm 0.0005	26.72 \pm 0.807
S8	0.637 \pm 0.210	0.6712 \pm 0.0255	9.94 \pm 0.023	1.05 \pm 0.0239	28.20 \pm 0.500
S9	0.685 \pm 0.0180	0.7061 \pm 0.0057	12.86 \pm 0.475	1.03 \pm 0.0259	26.87 \pm 0.8352

A

B

C

Figure 4: DSC thermograms of A-Eprosartan Mesylate, B- PEG 4000 and C- physical mixture.

Hausner ratio

Hausner ratio was determined by using the ρ_b is loose bulk density and ρ_t is tapped bulk density. Hausner ratio is greater than 1.25 is considered to be an indication of poor flow ability. Hausner ratio = ρ_t / ρ_b

Evaluation of tablets

Hardness test

Hardness indicates the ability of a tablet to withstand mechanical shocks while handling. The hardness of the tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm². Three tablets were randomly picked and hardness of the tablets was determined values are reported .

Weight variation

Table 11: Results of Post compression evaluation of Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer.

Batch No.	Thickness (mm) ±SD	Hardness (kg/cm ²) ±SD	Friability (%)	Weight variation (%)±SD	Drug content (%)
S1	4.66±0.011	4.13±0.117	1.0	0.181±0.695	86.19±0.012
S2	4.62±0.015	4.40±0.122	0.27	0.120±0.737	87.77±0.036
S3	4.63±0.011	4.70±0.07	0.30	0.132±1.298	88.38±0.006
S4	6.65±0.007	4.10±0.07	0.43	0.213±0.520	89.31±0.0013
S5	4.66±0.02	4.20±0.07	0.28	0.213±0.422	85.95±0.071
S6	4.66±0.011	4.16±0.108	0.27	0.169±0.575	88.88±0.140
S7	4.61±0.012	4.23±0.108	0.22	0.238±0.425	95.10±0.0435
S8	4.62±0.0122	4.33±0.108	0.33	0.238±0.284	95.07±0.121
S9	4.61±0.02	4.16±0.105	0.43	0.266±0.341	95.71±0.003

Table 12: Results of Post compression evaluation Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer.

Time (min)	Formulation Batches (% CDR ±SD)								
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9
1	3.80	10.55	2.04	2.01	2.23	1.01	7.89	2.70	8.85
2	6.30	12.04	8.07	9.18	3.69	4.90	8.86	6.01	27.97
3	13.79	12.78	15.37	11.49	5.61	12.66	14.05	9.33	33.88
4	17.84	14.08	16.80	11.96	9.97	20.42	27.71	9.58	34.82
5	19.86	19.47	22.36	29.08	17.30	32.55	28.06	29.47	37.89
6	20.06	25.22	27.76	36.49	23.58	37.41	39.06	36.36	50.64
7	25.93	29.68	33.00	40.19	28.29	41.30	46.95	42.74	63.15
8	32.41	35.80	36.81	48.99	34.75	49.06	65.95	53.19	78.74
9	33.22	56.41	54.91	73.29	55.33	75.03	68.30	79.72	82.99
10	63.76	63.09	61.11	74.68	60.57	79.40	68.31	82.78	87.71
11	65.59	65.88	61.43	76.31	61.63	80.14	72.16	84.07	93.38
12	68.01	71.44	67.45	89.04	67.02	86.14	82.15	89.68	97.86

Figure 5: Dissolution profiles of Eprosartan Mesylate SR layer.

Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and average weight was calculated.

Then individual tablet were weighted and individual weight was compared with an average weight.

Thickness

Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and their thickness was measured by using vernier calliper. Thickness of three tablets from each batch was measured and mean was calculated.

Friability

Roche friabilator was used for the purpose. Twenty tablets were weighed and placed in the Roche friabilator, which was then operated for 25 rpm for 4 min. After revolution tablets were deducted and reweighed. Compressed tablets should not lose more than 1% of their weight. Values are reported. The percentage friability was measured using the formula, % F = {1-(Wo/W)} ×100

Drug Content

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered. An amount of powder equivalent to 8 mg of Eprosartan Mesylate was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer [pH 6.8]. It was

Table 13: Precompression & Postcompression parameter of bilayer tablet.

Sr. No.	Precompression parameters	Observation	Precompression parameters	Observation
1	Bulk density (gm/ml)	0.5444±0.012	% Weight variation (mg)	Complies
2	Tapped density (gm/ml)	0.7472±0.025	Thickness (mm)	6.05±0.23
3	Compressibility index %	20.18±0.010	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	5-6
4	Hausner's ratio	0.729±0.158	Friability (%)	0.290
5	Angle of repose	28.81±0.186	Drug content (%) of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Tablet	97.91
6	-	-	Drug content (%) of Eprosartan Mesylate SR Tablet	95.81
7	-	-	Disintegration Time of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Tablet (Min)	6.30

Table 16: Stability study of optimized formulation.

Stability parameter at 40±2 °C/ 75±5% RH	Time (Days)			
	0	30	60	90
Eprosartan Mesylate Bilayer tablet				
1) Disintegration of Eprosartan MesylateIR layer (Min.)	6.31	6.18	6.13	6.05
2) Drug content %	97.91	97.89	97.84	97.70
3) In vitro dissolution	98.82	98.80	98.21	98.10

shaken by mechanical means for 1 hr. Then it was filtered through a whatman filter paper. From this resulted solution 1ml was taken, diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 and absorbance was measured against blank at 234 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. From the absorbance values, amount of drug present in the given tablet was calculated using calibration curve. Procedure was repeated by using two or more tablets from the same formulation and the average value of all three tablets were calculated.

In vitro drug release study

In vitro drug release study was performed using dissolution apparatus USP type II paddle method with a stirring speed 50 rpm at 37.0 ± 0.5 °C in 900 ml of 0.1 N HCL for immediate release upto 1 hr and 6.8 pH phosphate buffer up to 12 hr for sustain release. The samples were collected at per selected time intervals with replacement of equal volume of dissolution media. The absorbance of collected samples was measured spectrophotometrically at 230 nm. *Stability Studies (ICH Geneva 2003)*¹²

The optimized formulation was subjected for two month stability study according to ICH guidelines. The selected formulations were packed in aluminium foils, which were in wide mouth bottles closed tightly. They were then stored at room temperature 40°C / 75% RH for 2 months and evaluated for their permeation study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bilayer tablet is one of the approaches for biphasic release system. Attempts have been made for preparation of biphasic release with variable concentration of superdisintegrant in IR layer and rate retarding polymer in SR layer for adjusting release pattern according to marketed formulation and USP guidelines of Eprosartan Mesylate Sustained release tablet. In the bilayer tablet one of the layers was formulated with superdisintegrant CCS and SSG for immediate drug release while another layer

was formulated with the hydrophilic polymer HPMC and HPMC K100M for extended drug release.

FTIR Spectroscopy

Eprosartan Mesylate and Optimized formulation same characteristic peaks were observed for the drug-excipients mixture, indicating that no chemical reaction or interaction between the drug and excipients took place. The FTIR spectra of pure Eprosartan Mesylate showed characteristics peaks at 689.60 cm⁻¹ which indicates Trans **RCH=CHR** stretching vibration. 851.57 cm⁻¹ indicates that **R-COOH** group is present, 1214.15 cm⁻¹ indicates **C=O** bond is present, 1417.80 cm⁻¹ indicates Ar- **C-C** group is present. 950.12 cm⁻¹ indicates **O-H** group is present.

Solubility Study

The maximum solubility was observed at ratio 1:3. The results are shown in table no: 05.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction

The PXRD Pattern of EPM is shown in Figure 8.13. Based on the diffractogram it can be suggested that EPM is present in its crystalline form since it exhibits several well defined peaks at a diffractogram angle of 2θ. The strong peak at 2θ of 22.14 and d value 9.01 was highly intense peak with 100% intensity indicating presence of crystalline EPM. EPM: PEG 4000

PXRD spectra of Eprosartan Mesylate Solid dispersion (figure 5) the entire characteristic peaks which were shown by the drug were absent in the solid dispersion with PEG 4000. The intense peak at 13.64° indicating crystalline nature of drug. X-ray diffraction pattern SD showed absence of these distinct peaks; it was indicating that crystalline nature of drug was reduced.

*Differential Scanning Calorimetry*⁶

DSC thermograph of EPM is shown in figure 6(A) which shows melting endotherm at 254.20°C i.e. melting point and crystalline state of drug. DSC thermograph of EPM: PEG 4000 is shown in figure 6(C). Thermograph showed melting endotherm at 250°C slightly less than melting point

of EPM 254⁰c indicating formation of stable LSC. No crystallization peak was observed. It can be predicted that small crystalline portion of EPM existed in this LSC melted at temperature lower than the melting point of pure EPM. The melting endotherm could not be clearly observed. A small exothermic peak was observed near melting point of EPM indicating crystallinity of EPM: PEG 4000 mixture.

Evaluation parameters of powder blend for IR & SR layers

The powder blends of both IR and CR layers of different formulations of bilayer tablets were

Evaluated for various physical properties (Table 7&8). The bulk densities for the powder blend of IR and SR layer of various formulations values indicated satisfactory flow behaviour.

Evaluation of optimized bilayer tablet of Eprosartan Mesylate IR layer and Eprosartan Mesylate SR Layer

Optimized bilayer tablet was prepared from optimized Formulation of Eprosartan Mesylate IR Layer (I8) and Eprosartan Mesylate SR Layer (S9). This tablet was subjected only to in vitro drug release study to check the drug release was as per specifications given in official compendia or not.

Evaluation of precompression and post compression parameters of Bilayer Tablet

All the Prepared tablet formulations were subjected for precompression and post compression evaluation such as bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio and Carr's index. Results of precompression evaluations of formulation mixtures are shown in table no.13. From the results of Compressibility (Carr's) index and Hausner's ratio it can be clearly concluded that the Eprosartan Mesylate tablet blend were having excellent flow properties, fair to good compressibility All the prepared bilayer tablets were subjected to compendial test for post compression evaluation such as friability, hardness, thickness, uniformity of weight, disintegration time & content uniformity results. Evaluation optimized batch is given in table no.13.

Stability study

Optimized formulations of bilayer tablet were subjected to stability studies as per ICH guidelines. Various parameters such as Physical appearance, drug content, disintegration time and in vitro dissolution profile release were measured before and after 30, 60 and 90 days of stability. Results of stability studies are shown in table no.16. Physical appearances of all formulations were unaffected or did not show any significant changes.

Results of stability studies showed that there is no significant change in above mentioned parameters after elevated temperature and humidity conditions during stability studies. Thus it can be proved from the stability studies that the prepared formulation is stable and not much affected by elevated humidity and temperature conditions.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Based on the above study, it can be concluded that Eprosartan Mesylate, a conventional drug for

Hypertension (ACE Inhibitor) can be successfully formulated in the form of bilayer tablet by optimizing drug polymer ratio using different grades of common polymers like HPMC, HPMC K 100 M etc. This is basically done to improve bioavailability of the drug and better therapeutic compliance. The sustained layer of the drug showed steady state release behaviour over a prolonged duration of time which may reduce dose related side effects. In future, natural biodegradable polymers can be used to improve therapeutic efficacy of the drug and further minimizing side effects.

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